

**NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY**

**7TH ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
COMMUNICATION AND INFORMATION SCIENCE**

**Communication and Information Science
In Fostering National Development In a
Science, Technology, Engineering and
Mathematics (STEM) Environment**

**21 - 24 August 2017
Caribbea Bay, Kariba, Zimbabwe**

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT SERVICES: AN INVESTIGATION OF RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AT THE NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (NUST)

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Abstract

The study sought to gain a holistic understanding of NUST researcher's data management practices in the Faculty of Applied Sciences and the faculty of communication and information science as they relate to the creation, management, and preservation of research data with a view to introduce research data management services (RDMS). A mixed methods convergent parallel research design employing some elements of the Data Asset Framework (DAF) was adopted for the study. Data was gathered through questionnaires and face to face interviews. Study findings revealed that some data were still being collected in out-dated formats; data management practices were guided by intuition rather than informed by good practice and data were sometimes neglected once a project is complete. The findings of the study also showed a general lack of data sharing through repositories and journals in favour of sharing via personal communication. Concerns among researchers about the amount of time required in preparing data for sharing and the potential for misuse of data hindered them from sharing research data. Researchers also rarely created metadata or other documentation for data. Data storage needs and behaviours varied, with different storage devices being used at different research lifecycle stages. Researchers identified a number of services that they would find valuable including assistance with data management planning and backup/storage services. The findings of the study may be used to inform development of research data management services at NUST Library.

Keywords: Research; data management; universities; data sharing

1. Introduction

The escalating simplicity and swiftness with which researchers can collect large, complex data sets is outpacing their development of the knowledge and skills that are necessary to properly manage them (Whitmire, Boock and Sutton, 2015; Borgman, 2015; Coates, 2014). Jahnke and Asher (n.d) point out that, new opportunities that are being brought about by advancing digital technologies such as creation of data sets that enable sophisticated analyses, are now being endangered by haphazard data management and preservation strategies. Services related to supporting researchers in their data management, both short- and long- term, have in many cases been found to be lacking. Jones, Ball and Ekmekcioglu (2008) point out that although vast quantities of data are being created within higher education; few institutions have formal

strategies in place for curating these research outputs in the long-term. Libraries, in conjunction with research offices on campus, are now seen as ideal centres for supporting academic researchers in their research data management needs. While librarians have conventionally provided research support through collection development, information literacy education and search strategy consultation (Bresnahan, and Johnson, 2013), this role is expanding to encompass management of research data within the new research landscape.

Libraries particularly academic research libraries have now realised that research data is part of the global knowledge base that they are expected to manage and should therefore assume new roles in research data management. This is what Pasipamire (2015) describes as “moving away from ‘life support’ to a more critical role”. As a result many libraries especially in developed countries are considering adding new services such as data management and open access publishing support, to meet an increasingly diverse set of researchers' information needs and to help with the research mission of their institutions (Henderson ME and Knott, 2015; Bresnahan and Johnson, 2013). However in order to do this libraries should be aware of current research data practices in order to provide needed data services to researchers. Development of effective data management services requires that domain-specific researchers and librarians find a mature understanding of data curation requirements, practices and procedures (Shakeri, 2013).

The National University of Science and Technology (NUST) Library included research data management (RDM) as part of its 2016 annual training programme of library staff with the goal of introducing data services in the future. However as remarked by Ray (2014), developing data services requires libraries to invest time and effort to understand current practices with data; when, how, and why these practices are performed and the gaps between current and ideal practice from the perspective of the researcher. In the words of Orgier et.al (2014) “At the heart of every institutional research-related service lies the need to understand the nature and context of the data produced by its researchers”. Without this understanding data services offered by the library may not resonate with the needs of the intended audiences and may go unused. In this regard, this study sought to explore NUST researchers' data management practices. The results of the study are meant to inform the development of research data services (RDS) at the institution

2. Literature review

Several RDM assessment methodologies, tools and instruments have been used to understand research data management practices by researchers in universities. Wright et al. (2013) utilised the data curation profiles (DCPs) to design the Datastar Dataset Registry research data management service at the Cornell University Library (CU) to support basic discovery of datasets. The study involved conducting structured interviews with researchers at CU and Washington University in St. Louis (WUSTL) using the Data Curation Profile (DCP) interview instrument to inform the ongoing development of a data registry. The study findings were useful to identify services that were likely to be valued and utilized across different research areas. Zilinski and Lorenz, (2012) studied data management and practices of researchers at University of South Florida, United States in an effort to select the best digital asset management systems (DAMS) to assist researchers with storing their data sets and developing data management plans. Preliminary study results led the project team to further investigate two open-source DAMS that would best fit the university's researchers. Akers and Doty

(2012) conducted a survey to gather information on researchers' practices and perspectives in order to guide development of library services to support the management of research data at Emory University.

Beagrie, et al. (2009) conducted a United Kingdom Research Data Service (UKRDS) Feasibility Study to assess the feasibility and costs of developing and maintaining a national shared digital research data service for the UK Higher Education sector. From the outset it was recognised that the scope and requirements for a UKRDS should be determined primarily by researchers themselves. Therefore a major component of the feasibility study for UKRDS was the Survey of the researcher viewpoint conducted in collaboration with the Universities of Bristol, Leeds, Leicester and Oxford. This involved researchers and staff from central services in the four universities. Their views were sought on the potential scope and requirements and how a national shared data service could help their research, their institution, and UK research competitiveness.

Alexogiannopoulos, McKenney and Pickton (2010) used the Data Asset Framework (DAF) methodology at Northampton University, to investigate the types of data held by researchers throughout the university researchers, existing data management practices, and the risks associated with these practices. Study findings showed that most researchers used Microsoft software for creating documents and spreadsheets while a great variation existed in the file types used for databases, audio and video files. Data storage needs and behaviours also varied throughout the research lifecycle, with different storage devices being prominent at the data collection, analysis and project completion stages. Study findings also revealed that data were still being collected in out-dated formats; data management practices were guided by intuition rather than informed by good practice; data were sometimes neglected once a project is complete; the universities shared server space was under-exploited; and researchers were sometimes ill informed, or even misinformed, of the services available to them.

Important to note is that all these studies have a striking homogeneity including: a general lack of data sharing through repositories and journals in favour of sharing via personal communication, researchers rarely creating metadata or other documentation for data, backup and storage practices that are of questionable efficacy and on questionable media, and concerns among researchers about the amount of time required to prepare data for sharing and the potential for misuse of data. However these studies are not easily generalisable in a developing country context where the volume and nature of research might be different.

3. Research methodology

A mixed methods convergent parallel research design employing some elements of the Data Asset Framework (DAF) was adopted for the study. The purpose of the convergent design was to best understand or develop more complete understanding of the research problem by obtaining different but complementary data. According to Creswell, Vicki and Clark (2011) the convergent design is used when the researcher wants to triangulate methods by directly comparing and contrasting quantitative statistical results with qualitative findings for corroboration and validation purposes. Data was gathered through questionnaires and face to face interviews. Interviews offered a depth of response not typically available using the questionnaires with regards to researchers' data management practices.

A pilot draft version of the questionnaire was prepared and distributed to 5 researchers in both faculties under the study to test the tool before questions were finalized. The survey instrument finally consisted of 20 core questions, which were adapted from a number of questionnaire instruments used in studies which adopted the Data Asset Framework (DAF) methodology. Questions were organized into 4 sections which included: types and size of data, data storage and retention, data access and sharing, data management plans and data services. The target population was 171, and composed of the Faculty of Applied Sciences with 127 academics and the Faculty of Communication and Information Science with 44.

The sample size was calculated by means of a table developed by the Universal Accreditation Board (2003), with a confidence level of 95% and a margin of error of + or – 5%. As the target population of academics in the two faculties was 171, the figure was rounded off to 170 so that it fits in within the sampling framework. The sample size was therefore found to be 127. In order to ensure that a representative number of academics were included for each faculty; the researchers adopted the proportionate allocation technique to draw samples from each faculty or stratum as well as department.

Table 1: Sampling Frame

Faculty	Total Population	Academics	Sample Size	% contribution to sample size
Applied Sciences	127		88	75
Communication and Information Science	44		30	25
	171		118	100

The sampling fraction f was also used to calculate the representative number of researchers per department as highlighted in the table below.

Table 2: Sampling Frame per Department

Faculty	Department	Total in each department	SampleSize	Contribution to Sample %
Applied Sciences	Applied Biology and Biochemistry	17	12	10.2
	Applied Chemistry	12	8	7
	Applied Mathematics	13	9	7.6
	Applied Physics	23	16	14
	Computer Science	15	10	8.5
	Environmental Science and Health	14	10	8.5
	Forest Resources and Wildlife Management	13	9	7.6
	Statistics and Operations Research	10	7	6
	Sport Science And Coaching	9	6	5.1
	Faculty Office	1	1	0.5
	Total	127	88	75%
CIS	Journalism and Media studies	13	9	7.6
	Library and Information Science	15	10	8.5
	Records and Archives Management	9	6	5.1
	Publishing Studies	7	5	4.2
	Total	44	30	25%
Total	171	118	100%	

4. Research findings

4.1 Response rate

A total of 118 questionnaires were distributed and 76 were returned representing 64% response rate. Fifteen researchers availed themselves to be interviewed out of 25 that were targeted.

4.2 Data types, size and storage

4.2.1 Types of digital research data generated

Researchers were asked to indicate the types of digital data generated in their research activities. The most common data type generated by Applied Sciences researchers were statistical data, (95%), spreadsheets (93%) and images (86%). In CIS 95% of the researchers generated images, 90% generated documents and 85% audio files.

4.2.2 Primary formats of data types

Respondents were asked to indicate the primary formats in which they stored different data types. Documents, Spreadsheets and images were the most common in all the two faculties with at least 70% of respondents having them. Databases were common in applied sciences with the majority (80%) utilising the statistical package for social scientist (SPSS). Few researchers generated only one type of data.

4.2.3 Sizes of data

In order to establish data storage requirements, participants were asked to indicate the size of data files they currently have. Eighty percent of CIS researchers had less than 10GB and 54 % of applied sciences researchers had 10GB to 100GB. Three percent and 10% of applied sciences and CIS researchers respectively, indicated that they did not know how much research data they were storing. Results indicated that researchers in applied sciences had larger quantities (i.e., Gigabytes) of data than researchers in CIS most of whom indicated that they had less than 10GB.

Figure 1: Data Sizes

4.2.4 Research projects per year

In order to plan for appropriate support of our researchers, the authors wanted to have a sense of how many projects on average our researchers lead each year. The majority of respondents in CIS (65%, n=13) indicated they are involved in at least 1 project per year. However (68%, n=38) of Applied Science researchers lead between 2-4 research projects in a year, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2: Research Projects per year

4.3 Data storage and retention

When asked how much of the data they held was of long term value, 46 % (n=26) of Applied Science researchers indicated 10GB to 50GB while 65% of CIS researchers indicated less than 10GB had long term value. The majority of CIS researchers (65%, n =13) planned to retain research data they currently have for up to five years. This is in contrast to the majority of applied sciences researchers (43%, n=24) who planned to retain their data indefinitely.

4.3.1 Data storage and backup systems

When asked where they stored their data, results indicated that the most common storage and backup systems for both faculties were hard disk drive of a privately owned computer; external hard drives such as memory stick/USB/Flash drive and cloud drive storage options such as Google drive and Drop box. Figure 3 below presents these results.

Figure 3: Data storage and backup systems

4.3.2 Projections of data storage requirements

Virtually all participants indicated that they expect their file sizes and their file storage increase in the future as highlighted in the Figure 4 below.

Figure 4: Data storage requirements

4.4 Data access and sharing

4.4.1 Accessing other researcher's data

Respondents were asked to indicate how they normally accessed other researcher's data. With regards to data access, most researchers in Applied Sciences (64%) said they accessed research data of other researchers through online access to source/discipline repositories and 85% of CIS researchers were unsure of how to access other researcher's data. (79%) from Applied Sciences indicated they were willing to share their research data publicly and already doing so and 15% said they don't currently but expect to do so in the future while 6% said no. Seventy five percent of researchers in CIS indicated that they were not willing to share their data, 20% expected to do so in the future while 5% were willing and already sharing data with others. Data interviews with the majority of researchers in applied sciences pointed towards a need to restrict access to their data for some period of time, or placed conditions on their willingness or ability to share their data with others.

Interviews with the 5 researchers in CIS revealed a strong unwillingness to share data. The top three reasons for not sharing data more widely were:

- 1) The data contain personal or sensitive information;
- 2) Researchers might not get credit for their data in terms of acknowledgement, citation, or authorship;
- 3) The data might be misinterpreted or misused.

This was corroborated by questionnaire findings which highlighted several reasons for not sharing data by CIS researchers which include but not limited to: Never considered it"; Not required by funder; Want to keep the data to do further research; Sensitive/confidential data; I don't want others to see my data; insufficient time; lack of standards for sharing data and I don't have permission to share the data.

The most common methods of sharing research data with others for applied sciences were by emailing data files (76%), using cloud storage services (72%) and sharing via academic social networks (70%).

4.5 Data management plans

Seventy five percent of researchers in Applied Sciences and 80% from CIS said they had never created data management plans for any of their research projects. Those that created data management plans did so because the research funders had specifically requested for them to do so. Major reasons for not creating data management plans by both faculties were lack of knowledge or experience on creating data management plans and absence of University data management policy and as well as time and effort required.

4.6 Data services

Researchers were asked to indicate which research data services they would like the library to introduce. The table below highlights the results.

As highlighted in Table 6 at least 75% of respondents in each faculty responded that they would be interested in all of the services proposed.

Table 6: Research data services

Research Data Service	Count			
	Applied Sciences		Social Sciences	
	Number	%	Number	%
Services for long term data storage and backup during active projects				
Information regarding data best practices	42	75	16	80
Information on Ethics, consent and legal issues with research data	43	77	15	75
Developing a research data management plan for a funding application	44	79	15	75
Copyright and intellectual property rights within a data context	48	86	16	80
Citing research data	45	80	17	85
Providing guidance for identifying appropriate discipline-specific repositories for research data	47	84	15	75
Sharing/Publishing Data services	42	75	16	80
Support in metadata creation and documentation of data	43	77	17	85
File naming and version control training	44	79	18	90

5. Discussion

5.1 Data types, sizes and storage

Whitmire,Boock and Sutton(2015) remark that when libraries are considering adding support services or training programmes on research data management, it is important to know ‘who’ is generating ‘what’ data types.The results indicate that both the Faculty of Applied Sciences and the Faculty of Communication and information Science generate a wide variety of data types. As expected, differences in the most common data types generated by the two faculties were evident. Although both faculties created digital text for quantitative research, the study established that more quantitative datasets was created by researchers in the Faculty of Applied Sciences.These disciplinary differences were also reported by Kennan and Markauskaite (2015) who stated that research data are heterogeneousmainly because of the discipline of a researcher.

In the physical sciences, data are generally gathered or produced by researchers through observations, experiments or by computer modelling. Borgaman (2007) cited by Kennan and Markauskaite (2015) provided examples of data from different scientific disciplines for example; specimens in biology, events and objects in physics and protein structures in chemistry. In the social sciences, researchers may gather or produce their own data from interviews, questionnaires and observations.

Although Cox and Pinfield (2014) remark that the prevalent use of powerful computing technology across disciplines means that an increasing number of researchers generate and use large data sets as part of their research processes, the study established that while researchers in the faculty of Communication and Information Science generated data which falls within the less than 50 gigabyte, researchers in the faculty of Applied sciences generated larger terabytes. Although some respondents said they did not know the volume of the research data they stored, generalising from those who knew, it can be concluded that researchers, especially in the Faculty of Communication and Information Science did not store large datasets. This view can be substantiated by the fact that respondents indicated that they lead at least more than 1 project in a year. The implications of such differences are that meeting the data storage needs of researchers at NUST would not pose as a challenge.

5.2 Data access and sharing

Previous studies by Kennan and Markauskaite (2015); Sutton et al (2015) Vineas et al (2014), Tenopir (2011) and Borgmann (2012) revealed that researchers were sceptical about research data sharing. According to Makani (2015), the notion of freely sharing research data is viewed as the most controversial aspect of research data management among scholars. While Vines et al (2014) cited by Makani 2015 reveal authors as poor stewards of their data and often unwilling to share their data, Borgmann 2012 notes that some researchers may never be 'done' with their data. It is not surprising that all these sentiments were confirmed as true in the current study. Researchers in the two faculties were adamant about sharing their raw data. Most social science researchers simply did not want others to see their data and others were concerned about privacy and confidentiality issues that may arise in publicly sharing research data. It is however important to note, as summarised by Kennan and Markauskaite (2015) that storing, describing and providing the possibility of sharing data is encouraged because data:

- are important to collect and therefore publicly funded research should be publicly available Murray-Rust (2008);
- may be unique and impossible to replicate, such as data representing a snapshot in time or space (Henty, Weaver, Bradbury and Porter 2008)
- can be reused to reproduce and validate original findings, to advance the original research or to open another line of inquiry (Witt 2010)
- can contribute to answering questions that may require inter-disciplinary problem solving (Cragin, Palmer, Carlson and Witt 2010)
- may be used to examine a phenomenon from different epistemic or social perspectives (Markauskaite 2010)

- may need to be collected and integrated from a variety of sources, beyond the scope of one research team, time or location (Borgmann 2007)

Therefore, considering the importance of data sharing, and the sentiments of researchers regarding data sharing, Makani (2015) asserts that research data sharing should be a consideration in the development of institutional research data management system services. Awareness should be raised on the public good of research data sharing.

5.3 Data management plans

More than ninety percent of the respondents in the study revealed that they did not create data management plans. The implications of these results are that researchers at NUST need to be trained on the role played by research data management planning in the research process. Several scholars recognise the importance of creating research data plans in the research life cycle. A report on research data management published by Boston University reveals that by managing research data, researchers will;

- Meet funding agency requirements
- Protect federal investment in research and development
- Expedite the scientific process; saving time and resources in the long run
- Use or re-use the value, the uniqueness, and the importance of data
- Ensure that research data and records are accurate, complete, authentic and reliable
- Ensure research integrity and replication
- Increase research efficiency
- Enhance data security and minimize the risk of data loss
- Prevent duplication of effort by enabling others to use your data
- Comply with practices conducted in industry and commerce

The report recommends that researchers need to think about data management as early as possible and throughout the research lifecycle. Data management is not a single task to be ticked off at any particular part of the research process, and is integral to the process of conducting research. Research funders are increasingly requiring researchers to meet certain data management criteria, and submit a technical or data management plan as part of their grant application.

Kennan and Markauskaite (2015) are of the notion that research data management plans assist researchers to estimate in advance how much and what kinds of storage they are likely to need at various stages of their research. Planning also encourages researchers to think about their data throughout potentially useful lifecycle of the data. Furthermore, the information in research project or programme management plans could be captured and used by institutions to inform their plans to develop institutional storage infrastructures and to identify skills and gaps, enabling institutions to, for example, recruit data specialists or plan to undertake training as required (Kennan and Markauskaite 2015).

5.4 Data services

According to Zhou et al (2015) research data services are those services which address the full data lifecycle, including data management plan, digital curation (selection, preservation,

maintenance, and archiving) and metadata creation and conversion. However, not every researcher possesses the ability to handle their research materials proficiently and the growing amount of scientific data also presents great challenges to them. Researchers often fail to shape clear, well-annotated datasets to accompany their research (i.e. with effective metadata), and may lose access to and misunderstand the original datasets over time (Dryad, 2010 cited by Zhou et al 2015). The findings in the study showed that researchers at NUST were in need of research data services which include;

- Services for long term data storage and backup during active projects
- Information regarding data best practices
- Information on Ethics, consent and legal issues with research data
- Developing a research data management plan for a funding application
- Copyright and intellectual property rights within a data context
- Citing research data
- Providing guidance for identifying appropriate discipline-specific repositories for research data
- Sharing/Publishing Data services
- Support in metadata creation and documentation of data
- File naming and version control training

These results give guidance on what services are to be prioritized when NUST library develops research data programmes.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

The conclusions that can be drawn from this study are that, there are differences in the most common data types generated by the Faculty of Applied Sciences and the Faculty of Communication and Information Science. These two faculties have varied storage needs which NUST Library should take into consideration when introducing research data management services. The study findings revealed that there was **uncertainty** surrounding the ownership of data; some data were still being collected in out-dated formats; data management practices were guided by intuition rather than informed by good practice and data were sometimes neglected once a project was completed.

The study found that there was skepticism among researchers when it came to data sharing. These sentiments were also felt by other researchers as evidenced in previous studies by Makani (2015); Kennan and Markauskaite (2015); Sutton et al (2015) Vineas et al (2014), Borgmann (2012) and Tenopir (2011). Findings of the study also showed a general lack of data sharing through repositories and journals in favour of sharing via personal communication. Concerns among researchers about the amount of time required in preparing data for sharing and the potential for misuse of data hindered them from sharing research data. Researchers also rarely created metadata or other documentation for data. These findings have strong implications for introducing research data management services at NUST Library. The recommendations drawn from these conclusions are that NUST Library:

- i. Should support the lifecycle for research data by providing services for storage, discovery and permanent access.
- ii. Get involved in subject specific data management practice.
- iii. Create Data Librarian posts and develop professional staff skills for data librarianship.
- iv. Offer research data management support, including data management plans for grant applications, intellectual property rights advice and information materials. Assist faculty with data management plans and the integration of data management into the curriculum.
- v. Tailor research data services to meet the varying needs of researchers in differing disciplines using differing methodologies.

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